

Entrepreneurship Education in Library and Information Science and Marketing of Library Services: Issues in Nigeria

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Abstract: *There has been a need to expand library career opportunities given the small growth of libraries and information centers in developing countries like Nigeria. The present economic realities and the challenges in labor market in Nigeria also justify the need to equip undergraduates with the basic entrepreneurial skills that would enable them to be self-employed after graduation. Moreover, users of library no longer see the need to visit the library because library services are not attractive and packaged in ways preferred by them. There is therefore, the need to make library services attractive and profitable; this will require turning library services into marketable products that can be put up for sale to generate income for the library, this is also expected to attract more users into the library. Marketing of library services and entrepreneurship education in Nigerian library schools, are faced with issues like product repackaging, pricing, funding raising for entrepreneurship training, lobbying, advocacy strategies by the library etc.,. All these must be addressed by any library or library school that wishes to engage in marketing of its services and adding entrepreneurship education in it curriculum.*

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship education, marketing of library services, library education*

I. Introduction

Entrepreneurship refers to an individual's ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, sense of initiation, innovation and risk-taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage project in order to achieve objectives. Entrepreneurship as a concept has been described by Hisrich (2008) as a process of creating something new with value, devoting necessary time and effort, assuring of accompany of financial psychic, and social risks, and receiving the rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Morrision (2006) defines entrepreneurship as the willingness and ability of a person or persons to acquire education skills to explore and exploit investment opportunities, establish and manage a successful business enterprise. Nwangwu (2007) says it is a process of bringing together the factors of production which include land, labor and capital so as to provide a product or services for the public consumption. It is obvious from the above definitions that entrepreneurship is a set of skills an individual acquire that make him innovative, and capable of transforming the factors of production into something new, and which will be beneficial to the society, and at the same time bring monetary value to the individual. An entrepreneur is skilled in the use of available resources to create something new and which can sustain the individual or provide him a means of livelihood.

The inclusion of entrepreneurship education in the curriculum of tertiary institution is meant to increase the innovation and creativity level in students, so that at the end of their study in the institution they will be able to provide for themselves a means of living, create job opportunities for others, add value to the life and their communities and also, assist in the development of their nation. Many reasons have been pointed out to justify the inclusion of entrepreneurship education in the curriculum of tertiary institutions, more importantly, in Library and Information Science. Entrepreneurship education according to Paul (2005) stands to achieve the following objectives: offers functional skills for the youth that will enable them to be self-employed and self-reliant; provide the youth graduates with adequate training that will enable them to be creative and innovative in identifying novel business opportunities; serve as a catalyst for economic growth and development; offer tertiary institution graduate with adequate training in risk management to make certain bearing feasible; reduce high rate of poverty; employment generation; provide the young graduates with enough training and support that will enable them to establish a career in small and medium size business; inculcate the spirit of perseverance in the youths and adults that will enable them to persist in any business venture they may embark on; and create smooth transition from traditional to a modern industrial economy.

The introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has revolutionized service provision and service delivery in libraries. The issue of marketing of library services has been an unending debate because many hold it that the library is meant to provide services that are not profit targeted or centered. Librarians of this present age

however, are faced with constant pressure of becoming more competitive and to provide information products and services to diverse users that need them. The challenges of budget cuts, increased user base, the rapid growth of material, rising costs, networking demands, competition by database vendors, and complexity in information requirements are also forcing librarianship professionals to adopt marketing strategies in order to improve the management of their library and information centre's (Madhusudhan, 2008). Umar (2009) expressed that globalization and growth of ICTs have revolutionized the world in such a way that professions including Library and Information Science have to define their skills and competencies in order to create and gain competitive advantage. Ali (2009) reported on some marketing competencies needed in library and information science business to include: ability to select a strategic location for LIS business based services, properly attended to customer's questions and library service needs, ability to select new LIS books and repackaging new IT distribution outlets/supplies. Also, is librarianship broadcasting, information broker, indexing and abstracting, book trade, librarians as editors, internet services etc.

The objectives of marketing of library services are rooted in the fact that it will help the library to gain self-sufficiency; it will help to ensure clientele satisfaction; it increase library effectiveness in relation to their services provision; it will help to anticipate the desires and requirements of actual and potential library users and fulfill them; it will help to fulfill library objectives; it will make the library to make profit through their services and finally, it will ensure the survival of the library. Vishwa Mohan, Shrinivas and Shashikala (1996; 16) in their survey on information marketing by university libraries in India says that marketing is essential in library for the following reasons: promotion of the use of information resources; create perception of need and thereby create demand; ensure the optimum use of information improve the image and status of the libraries and library professionals; tackle the problems of rising costs of reading materials, journals, and databases; cope with the information explosion; introduce cutting-edge information technology systems in library services; balance shrinking funds; save libraries from devaluation; save libraries from declining reader-support; uphold the dictum that information is power.

The introduction of marketing in library service delivery and entrepreneurship education in Library and Information Science education are to project the profession; librarianship. To make the profession more competitive and also to give students studying librarianship the opportunity of acquiring innovative and creative skills capable of making them establish an independent venture of business at a profitable level and ultimately, to ensure sustainable living.

II. Marketing of Library Services: Issues in Nigeria

Marketing is a broad area that covers several issues like: market research and customer analysis, development of product and services, pricing, distribution, promotion and evaluation of products.

2.1. Market research and customer analysis

It is a major step for the library to do a survey of the market situation and condition, which imply; a survey into what the market trend is and on what the library can offer for sale that will sell. The library and information organization render several services to users that can be repackaged as product for sale. The library must show what it wishes to sale and should undertake a feasibility study to know if it is what the users market wants. Another phase is that of customer analysis. A product might be good and useful but question on if the customers want such product? When do they want it? Where? How do they want the product to be packaged or presented and many more are analyzed.

2.2. Development of product and services

The library has many products and services to market. A product is anything that can be offered to the market or public for sale to satisfy a need. A large assortment of materials, services and programmes constitute the library's product (Madhusudhan, 2008). The library on its part needs to identify these services. Issa, Uzuegbu and Nwosu (2014) categorize the various LIS based entrepreneurial opportunities to include: libraries and information centre equipment supply business; publishing and printing business; information brokerage business; courier service business; LIS consultancy business; rural information provision business; stationery business; reprographic and allied business; art gallery business; vendor business; freelance information business and, ICT- based business. Afolabi (1984) and Ochogwo (2015) made a list of self-employment opportunities for libraries and LIS graduates to include book related businesses such as book selling, binding and abstracting; fee based businesses such as information brokerage, courier services and compilation of guides; engagement in information and communication technology such as running of cyber café, engaging in film business such as cinema business, project hiring, DVD, CD-ROM sales, rent, dub, and the likes; and event coverage such as photo and video coverage at occasions and ceremonies, including documentation of indigenous knowledge.

2.3. Pricing

Price is used to balance supply and demand, to be a stimulus, and to distribute income (Rowley, 2001). Pricing is the allocation of worth and value to library product and services to be offered for sale. After the library product has been identified, the next step is to fix a value on such product and services in relation to how such product is sought after or demanded by users. Pricing most times is determined based on the time and effort a user would have used originally to access such information product or the time and effort spent by the library/librarian to make such information product and services available.

2.4. Distribution

Distribution covers a line and channel employed by the library in reaching the users in need of library's product. The library must identify various channels of disseminating information. Examples of this can include selective dissemination of information, information to target audience, referral service, exchange relation, calling on phone, sending of mails. Libraries can engage in mobile library operation, book home delivery, library book exhibitions, having book shops and kiosks in the focused community or area, taking books to schools and other area of demand, etc.

2.5. Promotion

Promotion is essentially the means of informing the users what you do and what you can do. The benefits for those who promote their library services include: increased usage, increased value in the organization, education of users and changed perceptions. Promotional channel can take the form of publicity, advertisement, library communication, announcements, public relations, the internet, mails, build good relationship with users, and create a welcoming environment for users, using mass media, newsletters and leaflets.

2.6. Evaluation of product

Regular and constant appraisal of the product offered by the library to users is required to determine the benefit derived by users from the information product and services provided. Every organization either profit making or non-profit making ones that renders public services or sale product understand the importance of evaluation. By evaluation of product, a library is able to decide on other methods or mode of their product delivery and supply, it gets response from users of its product, which makes the library to identify its strengths and weaknesses so as to take necessary steps and actions.

Nigerian libraries must inevitably consider possibilities of profit generation for their sustenance and survival. Areas of information product generation and sales must be identified and potential user known, a good market survey must be undertaken to know what is wanted, in what form, and for how much, only then can the library remain relevant, project its image and proves to the world that it can stand the demand of the 21st century.

III. Entrepreneurship Education in Library and Information Science (LIS): Issues in Nigeria

Another of the major trends in the practice of library and information science is the inclusion of entrepreneurship education in library. The new era librarian and librarianship students are those that can create ideas, innovations and knowledge into what can yield profit. They are also capable of working in a hybrid world of presenting library services in such a manner that would attract users to making use of the library, while, making gain at the same time. Entrepreneurship education in Library and Information Science (LIS) however come with issues which call for attention. Some of these issues are lobbying, advocacy, issues of capital creation and generation, access to financial services, competition, advertisement and many more.

3.1. Advocacy

Advocacy is defined as any action that speaks in favor of, recommends, argues for a cause, supports or defends, or pleads on behalf of others. Also in a clear term, advocacy can simply be referred to advertisement, promotion or the act of marketing a product as a result of its importance or value with a planned and organised action. It is the process of creating awareness and passing information through communication to stimulate a positive response toward a working phenomenon (Omoike and Ikegune, 2018). The term advocacy encompasses a whole range of methods and approaches used to change those policies and practices, attitudes and behaviors that function as obstacles to development and poverty eradication (on-line document, www.afj.org).

Advocacy is a social change process that focuses on the causes of poverty, failure, weakness etc, and seeks change at this level. At its best, the process of advocacy should involve those people who are affected by the problems identified; increase cooperation between parties and other civil groups; and expand the space for open discussion between organizations, governments and institutions. Advocacy consists of actions designed to draw institutional and community's attention to an issue and to direct policy-makers to a solution. It consists of legal and political activities that influence the shape and practice of laws. Advocacy initiatives require organization, strategic thinking, information,

communication, outreach and mobilization. Library management has a role to play and this involves several strategies employed by the library to get what it desire even in austere situations. Many a time, the benefits and resources that are needed by the library for development are denied it, it is imperative therefore for the library to take steps to fight against decisions that will deny it these benefits and resources. To fight, the library must research into issues, causes and their consequences on it, identify solutions and changes needed, power mapping and analyzing stakeholders interest, outlining methods of approach, setting timetable of activities and assigning responsibilities. Advocacy is needed in library for widespread and sustainable change, to ensure that sustainable programmes are not denied the library and stopped abruptly and finally, to defend the library and its programmes from adverse policy changes (Veneklasen and Miller, 2002).

3.2 Lobbying

Lobbying is yet another way by which the library can get what it desires and needs to ensure effective information delivery services to communities it serves. A group, organization or association engaged in trying to influence legislators or other public officials in favour of a specific cause. Originally the term referred to persons frequenting the lobbies or corridors of government buildings in order to speak to lawmakers. Mostly, lobbying is limited to describing direct attempts to influence policy makers, public officials or other decision makers through personal interviews and persuasion. However, some people use the term inter-changeably with advocacy and for them it covers all attempts to influence directly or indirectly any policy, practice or government activity, and includes any attempt to influence legislators, their staff, civil servants, and members of regulatory agencies. Through advocacy and lobbying, the library can influence the decisions and draw attention of their needs to parties that will facilitate its process and attainment. For the library to have greater lobbying effect, it must be clear of what it want, know the views of the parties to be lobbied, have reasons why they should change their minds, the library must build relationship and use negotiation strategies.

3.3. Campaign

This is said as advertisement in profit making organizations but non-profit organizations embark on campaigns and public relation means to project their products and services, and also to reach wider audience. The library can make its services known by organizing campaigns using leaflet and other materials for public distribution; posters or advertisement; public meetings; media work-newspaper, video or TV; stunts or events to attract media attention; using celebrities to support your cause; letter writing campaigns; petitions; competitions; mass lobbies and demonstrations; mass events- facts, cycle rider, street theatre etc., running an active website, T-shirt, overhead transparencies; e-mails and many more. The library must first understand why the need to campaign, it must decide target audience, what media or channel to use, the message must be developed (using simple pictures or signs), budget must be high marked for the campaign and implementation must follow.

3.4. Fund raising and generation

Nonprofit organizations need resources to achieve organizational goals and fulfill their mission, as well as to grow and develop their activities. The fundamental categories of required resources are (Andreasen and Kotler, 2008): financial resources (including revenues from products and services) and human resources (employees and volunteers). Among those, the success in raising funds is crucial to the performance of nonprofit organizations. Fundraising, as an activity is directed toward securing also for graduates to engage in lucrative entrepreneurship services, they will need adequate capital to commence any form of information businesses they wish to engage in. They may need to purchase the ICTs that will guarantee them access to current and relevant information resources that they need to provide information services to customers. Andreasen and Kotler (2008) define fundraising as an activity of collecting financial resources and identify the main sources of funds. They emphasize that the nonprofit sector (fundraising included) has gone through three orientation phases in its development, as related to the product, sales and marketing orientation. Pavičić (2003) defines fundraising in terms of its activities and believes that it could be viewed not only as a part of the overall marketing strategy, but also as a separate strategic and implementation strategic activity. The library needs fund to run its activities and also ensure that it provides information services that can be marketable, it therefore needs to look for means of generating fund in order to effectively function. Warwick (1999) points out that fundraising can do much more than simply provide funds for the organization, as the fundraising objectives may include growth (creating a donor base), involvement (making donors active), visibility, raising organization's public profile), efficiency (reducing the cost of fundraising), stability, etc.

3.5. Public relations

Library in the aspect of public relations incorporates the interaction between the library and its customers. Public relations involve the interpersonal contact, which is to develop the communication of trust, mutual respect, perception, attitude and opinion to communicate the benefit of the library and its products. This associates a wide range of practice like editorial coverage of press, publishing of in-house journals, staff magazines, newsletters, and other publications. Library's image is developed through calendars, logos, letterheads, etc. Relationship with media is an important vehicle for the publicity and library personnel can produce seasonal press releases. Media interviews, bookmarks, posters, and displays are also tools for the publicity. The library services itself also can make publicity. Staff performances, face- to- face contact with users, and the quality and the structures of the library building are important factors. Customer care is another tool for the promotion of the library. This implies the training of staff to take client's attention to the library. Needs are fulfilled by setting priorities than insisting to apply the rule. Customer-care deals also with complaints and, this causes the user become more loyal advocate of the service. As another tool for promotion of the library, personal selling involves the presentation of conference papers, seminars, lectures, demonstrations, exhibitions, and other presentations. Sales force should be carefully recruited and administrated.

IV. Challenges to marketing of library services and entrepreneurship education in Library and Information Studies

Many library schools in Nigeria universities and polytechnics have not joined the clarion call to incorporate entrepreneurship course into their curriculum. Many library schools do not have functional ICT infrastructural facilities for proper teaching and training of entrepreneurs and (intrapreneuers). Most library schools do not have well equipped audio-visual laboratories. ICT laboratory, printing, publishing, book selling and library equipment laboratories that will arm the students with relevant skills that will prepare them to become entrepreneurs. Lack of funds has also been mentioned as part of the hindrances to the training of student's entrepreneurs. Not much budget is released for the library school programmes; there is also poor funding of library schools by heads of institutions of higher learning. The funds provided for purchase of equipment are not released by the appropriate authorities. Many heads of library schools and heads of institutions of higher learning lacks the spirit of advocacy and lobbying to get what they want from the funders or parent institutions.

Student's lack of practical and analytical thinking is yet another challenge to training of entrepreneurs and to the profession at large. The problem of massive unemployment of young library school graduates also pose problem. Many organizations that should have a library for library student graduates to work lack the library, therefore, a need for many young graduates rushing into many things at the same time. Students' admission and enrolment figure versus the teaching facilities for them is another critical challenge. It is not surprising to see 250 students in a classroom that is meant for only 50 students. The environment in Nigeria where the trained entrepreneurs would work is another clog in the wheel of students willing to be entrepreneurs. Factors like electricity, take off grants, equipment, workshop, dangerous competition terrain, corruption etc. make it so difficult for entrepreneurship business to thrive.

Another serious point in the challenges to entrepreneurship training in schools is the poor method of teaching and training employed in schools. There are no adequate infrastructure and equipment for quality research and learning. Trainings are now conducted manually and theoretically without real practical, the result will be graduates who cannot fit appropriate into industries and establish their own businesses.

V. Conclusion

The paradigm shift in library and information science education has become a paramount requirement in the information delivery business. This has called for a complete re-orientation in the training and retraining of educators, practitioners and even, the students in Library and Information Science (LIS). Doing this will require lots of changes in the LIS curriculum, these changes however, will need a great deal of capital generation in the library schools and the library to purchase relevant infrastructures for effective teaching and research. It is in this recognition that entrepreneurship education was incorporated into library education in Nigeria, librarians will acquire skills and knowledge that will enable them to create jobs and sustain themselves.

For graduates to engage in lucrative entrepreneurial services, they will need adequate capital to commence any form of information business. They will therefore need to purchase the ICTs tools that will guarantee access to current and relevant information resources that is needed to be provided to customers for a fee.

5.1. Prospects in Nigeria

The inclusion of entrepreneurship education and the turning of library services into products among library science schools in Nigeria and in the Nigerian libraries have great monetary values and prospects for the profession. The future library can build cinema houses, have hall for rent for social and educational purposes, the library can partner

with multinational companies to organize training, motivational talks, traditional or historical shows, the library can develop proposal or professional content and be presented to relevant firm for adoption and use, this can go in exchange for a particular fee. The library can generate money by presenting proposal of training to law makers exposing them to essentials of information retrieval and handling, this if approved will fetch the library money. The library can engage in information advocacy programmes that will be showcased on mass media for public enlightenment, this can be sponsored by organizations or even the government. This can bring the library to limelight and also ensure so money generation for the library.

5.2. Recommendations

- 1). The study recommends that library schools that have not incorporate entrepreneurship education into their curriculums should do so without delay in order to equip the students with the skills that will make them innovative, self-employed, job creators and contribute to national development.
- 2). The entrepreneurship education should not be theory alone, efforts should be made to provide adequate facilities that will enable the students to have practical experience and real life situations must be included in their course/programme so that the students can gather as much skills as necessary to start up on their own.
- 3). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) should be incorporated into the training of student entrepreneurs. This will enable them to function in line with 21st century requirement.
- 4). Heads of library schools should intensify on lobbying and advocacy skills, so that they will be able to generate enough funds to sustain the training of entrepreneurship education and also to be able to acquire adequate technology to transform library services into marketable products.
- 5). Managers, business tycoons and owners of established firms/industries should be invited from time to time to educate students and librarians on business strategies and corporation should be established among the library schools, libraries and these industries, so that students can go from time to time to see what obtain in a real work/business situations.
- 6). Adequate funding must be ensured by heads of library schools to support entrepreneurship education and training, and the production of information product to be marketed.
- 7). The library should at all-time seek users feedback; this can be effectively utilized to improve the quality of library services and products. The library can know the level of user's satisfaction and what their expectations are, thereby redesigning its services and repacking its products to adequately satisfy them.
- 8). The library should also make adequate market survey and to know what users, researcher and stakeholders have expressed demands for, this will make it set its goal aright.

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